

Characterization of highly filled thermosetting composite for the numerical prediction of residual stresses development during the production process of solid surface sanitary products

Joana Malheiro¹, Paulo Antunes¹, Helena Rocha¹, Manuel Grança², Nuno Marques^{2,3},
Andreia Antunes^{2,3}

¹PIEP, ²ROCA Group, ³SANITANA

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Introduction

- Traditionally, sanitary ware and kitchen counter tops are produced with ceramics and stone.
- Nowadays, solid surface composites are used as substitutes
 - thermoset resins filled with high percentage of mineral particles
- These thermoset resins are highly reactive, which makes the process control difficult due to the high temperature generated by the exothermic curing reaction. This intrinsic characteristic of the composite can lead to the development of residual stresses and strains, which should be minimized to assure an optimal structural behaviour of the products.

Objectives

- Predict stresses originated by the production process.
- Optimize the production process focusing on the stresses developed.

Numerical Approach

Workflow

Composite:

- ≈27% of Thermoset resin (polyester based)
- ≈73% of mineral Fillers (particles)

Assumptions:

- Casting is not simulated
- Mould is completely full (no voids)

Composite properties characterization

Thermal Conductivity

- MDSC (ASTM E1952)
- Isothermal runs (between 0°C and 90°C)
- Calibration material: polystyrene
- Specimen completely cured (with different thicknesses)
- $\lambda = f(T)$

Specific Heat

- DSC (ISO 11357-4)
- Dynamic runs (from -50°C to 220°C at 10°C/min): blank, synthetic sapphire and material
- Specimen uncured (no catalyst) and completely cured
- $C_p = f(T)$

Composite properties characterization

Curing Kinetics and Enthalpy

- DSC
- Dynamic runs (between -50°C and 250°C at different heating rates 5, 10, 20 and 30°C/min.)
- Specimen uncured
- Enthalpy = constant
- Friedman method (differential isoconversional method):

$$\ln\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right)_\alpha = \ln(k(T) \cdot f(\alpha)) = \ln(A_\alpha \cdot f(\alpha)) - \frac{E_{a\alpha}}{RT_\alpha}$$

- Model free (reaction model, f(α), unnecessary)
- Accounts for activation energy (Ea) dependency on conversion

Composite properties characterization

Glass Transition temperatures

- DSC
- For T_{g0} and $T_{g\infty}$: dynamic runs (between -90°C and 250°C at different heating rates)
- For $T_{g\alpha}$: Isothermal run (60°C for different periods of time) followed by dynamic run (between -50°C and 250°C at 5° C/min)
- Specimen uncured (no catalyst), partially cured and cured
- $T_g = f(\alpha)$

Degree of cure at gelation

- Oscillatory Rheometer (parallel plates) + DSC
- Isothermal runs (between 25°C and 60°C) + Conversion curves
- Specimen uncured
- Criteria: G' and G'' crossover point and $\tan(\delta) = 1$
- α at gel point

Composite properties characterization

Time – Temperature – Transformation (TTT) Diagram

Composite properties characterization

Chemical Shrinkage (CCS)

- Oscillatory Rheometer (parallel plates) + DSC
- Quasi-static isothermal runs (between 25°C and 60°C with 0.0N axial force) + Conversion curves
- Specimen uncured
- $\epsilon_V = \text{constant}$

$$+ \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{h - h_0}{h_0} \right)^3 - 1$$

Thermal Expansion (CTE)

- DMA
- Quasi-static compression mode, dynamic runs (between -10°C and 120°C at 1°C/min, with 0.0N axial force)
- Specimen completely cured
- CTE = $6,00E-03$

Composite properties characterization

Tensile properties

- Tensile test (ASTM D5083) + strain gauge
- Specimen completely cured
- Young Modulus, Poisson coefficient, tensile strength = $f(T)$

Compression properties

- Compression test (ISO 604)
- Specimen completely cured
- Compression strength = $f(T)$

NOTE:

- Standard for sanitary appliances EN 249 requires successive thermal shock cycles of 12°C and 75°C.

Numerical Model

Production cycle

- General production cycle:
 - Casting at room temperature (1)
 - First curing stage (with controlled temperature), up to gel point (before demoulding) (2)
 - Demoulding (3)
 - after 41 min, with rotation of the part and placed on wood like racks
 - Second curing stage with or without post-curing (after demoulding) (4 and/or 5)
- First and second curing stages are varied for optimization

Numerical Model

Boundary Conditions, Assumptions and Mesh

- Cavity of mould completely filled (no voids)
- Initial degree of cure: ≈ 0
- Convection coefficient: $10 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ (free convection of air with velocity $\approx 0 \text{ m/s}$, applied to all surfaces of mould and part exposed to air)
- Thermal condition at Interface: variation of HTC ($\text{W/m}^2\text{K}$) with temperature:

- Temperature cycle applied on surfaces exposed to air

- Initial temperature: 20°C (mould) and 30°C (composite)
- Demoulding at 41 min
- Rotation of the part
- Convection through wood board: $2.5 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$
- Before demoulding Locking condition: contact interface between mould and composite
- After demoulding Locking condition: isostatic (rigid body motion locked)
- Effect of gravity: 9.81 m/s^2

Mesh

- Solid tetra elements
- Part (element size): $\approx 1.5 - 3 \text{ mm}$
- Mould (element size): $\approx 5 \text{ mm}$

Numerical Results

- The location of the maximum residual stress is independent of the production cycle:

- Monitoring points:

Numerical Results

Scenario: isothermal at 25°C

- Fully cured
- Thin section does not reach Tg ∞
- High residual maximum stress

Numerical Results

Scenario: isothermal at 25°C with initial heating at 35°C

- Fully cured
- Whole part reach $T_{g\infty}$
- High residual maximum stress
- Initial heating does not improve residual stress

Numerical Results

Scenario: isothermal at 25°C with post-cure

- Fully cured
- Thin section does not reach Tg ∞ (before post-cure)
- High residual maximum stress
- Post-curing improve residual stress (but not enough)

Numerical Results

Scenario: with post-cure, without resting period

- Fully cured
- Thin section does not reach $T_{g\infty}$ (before post-cure)
- High residual maximum stress
- Eliminating resting period does not improve residual stress

Numerical Results

Scenario: with post-cure (extended cooling), without resting period

- Fully cured
- Whole part reach T_{g∞}
- Low residual maximum stress
- Extended cooling improves residual stress

Numerical Results

Scenario: cooling control with high initial temperature ($>T_{g\infty}$)

- Fully cured
- Whole part reach $T_{g\infty}$
- Low residual maximum stress

Numerical Results

Scenario: with post-cure (cooling control), with low initial temperature (25°C)

- Fully cured
- Thin section does not reach $T_{g\infty}$ (before post-cure)
- Low residual maximum stress

Conclusions

- Independently on the production cycle, cure is completed within 60 min, due to the heat generated by the exothermic curing reaction.
- The Tg_{∞} is only guaranteed if heating is added to the production cycle
- The magnitude of the maximum residual stress depends considerably on the thermal conditions of the production cycle.
- Post-cure, resting period and/or initial heating can be eliminated from the production cycle if:
 - Cooling is controlled
 - The Tg_{∞} is reached in the whole part

Thank you!

Questions?

(351) 253 510 075

joana.malheiro@piep.pt

www.piep.pt

PIEP - Pólo de Inovação em Engenharia de Polímeros,
Universidade do Minho, Campus de Azurém, Edifício 15
4800-058 Guimarães, Portugal

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